

Developing Video-Based English Textbook for Elementary School Students

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Abstract: In the Curriculum 2013, English is excluded from the Elementary School Subjects, especially for the State Elementary Schools. Some private elementary schools keep teaching English to their students. One of them is SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren. The English teachers found difficulty in providing a textbook that covers the students' need. This is a Research and Development (R & D) study which conducts the preliminary survey, designing and developing the prototype of the product, conducting limited testing and product validation, having a revision process and describing the research result. This study is aimed at finding out the students' need and providing a video-based textbook to teach English for the sixth grade students of SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren. The video-based textbook is developed based on the need analysis, syllabus and some theories related to teaching English to young learners.

Keywords: *video based, elementary school, young learner*

INTRODUCTION

In the curriculum 2013 English has been excluded from the elementary school subjects. The consideration behind that is young learners should master their mother tongue better than foreign language. Thus, English is included as an extracurricular. However, some private elementary schools keep teaching English to their students. It is due to private elementary schools have their own teaching and learning goals. One of the goals is preparing their students to face the globalization era. In that Era, everyone should master foreign language, especially English since it is an international language.

The new policy leads to a consideration that English teaching and learning will not be given much attention. However, some English teachers in private elementary

schools find difficulty in having suitable materials for their students. Therefore, they need teaching materials that cover the students' need. Besides, the teaching materials for young learners should be created as interesting as possible in order to build the students' motivation in learning English.

Teaching English to young learners is different from teaching it to adults. It can be observed from the characteristic of young learners. Cameron (2011: 1) states children are enthusiastic and lively as learners but they are also easy to lose their interest to the task that they find it difficult. Therefore, teachers should create the classroom management as interesting as possible in order to get their attention.

Besides, identifying young learners' need in acquiring foreign language is necessary to be investigated. Thomson (2010) states children first begin to sort out words involving concrete objects in the early age. When introduced into the L2 classroom, they "need very concrete vocabulary that connects with objects they can handle or see" (Cameron 2001: 81). In fact, young learners need to explore more on the vocabulary rather than the structure of a sentence.

Based on the need analysis obtained from focus group discussion, the English teachers said that the students are active and talkative. They like to get involved in fun and challenging activity. In teaching vocabulary they give more attention to visual aids rather than a text. The students also need a model especially when they acquire some expression of a dialogue related to their daily conversation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Teaching English to Young Learners

In Indonesia English is considered to be the first foreign language. For primary school students English is a new thing for them. New language is usually introduced, understood, practiced, and automatized orally and aurally. Therefore, the solution toward foreign language learning is that focus on words and interaction (Cameron, 2001:18).

Moreover, children have short attention. They are easy to get bored. Cameron (2003: 111) states that if the children are to be kept attentive and mentally active, the teacher must be alert and adaptive to their responses to tasks, adjusting activities and exploiting language learning opportunities that arise on the spot. Being able to diverge from a set lesson plan will allow for greater learning opportunities.

2. Teaching Materials for Young Learners

In order to achieve the goals of teaching, teacher should select proper materials for young learners. McGrath (2002: 107) states good texts as those that telling us something we do not know; they contain interesting content; they provoke a reaction. They are multiply exploitable because they lend themselves to tasks which are interesting as well as useful. It can be concluded that the materials used to teach young learners should be able to trigger the student's reaction and involvement.

3. Teaching English through Video

In order to achieve the goals of teaching, the teacher should formulate the materials as interesting as possible. One of them is video. In second language education, video materials have proved especially useful for a number of reasons. Video materials provide students with the opportunity to experience the target language in a more natural context (Williams and Lutes 2009: 2). Video in language learning may mean the use of popular films on video to provide content, and the use of smaller pieces of broadcast documentaries. Video can be used as listening and speaking tool to enhance the students' language ability (Intajuck 2001: 2).

According to some experts, there are some reasons why the teachers should use video in teaching English. Harmer (1991: 282) divides the benefits of using video into three dimensions, as follows:

a. Seeing language in use

One of the main advantages of video is that students do not just hear language, they see it too. This greatly aids comprehension, since for example general meaning and moods are often conveyed through expression, gesture, and other visual clues.

b. Cross cultural awareness

Video uniquely allows students look at situations far beyond their classrooms. This is especially useful if they want to see, for example, typical British “body language” when inviting someone out, or how Americans speak to waiters.

c. The power of creation

When students use video cameras themselves they are given the potential to create something memorable and enjoyable. The task of video-making can provoke genuinely creative and communicative uses of the language.

METHODOLOGY

This is a research and development study or it is known as R&D study. Borg and Gall (1983) states that, in terms of educational research and development, it deals with a process of developing and validating educational instruction. It is aimed to produce any kind of product for educational purposes. The product is developed based on the need analysis and document study in the preliminary stage. The product being developed was evaluated through feasibility test to see whether it is applicable or not.

Sugiono (2013: 297) states R&D study is a research methodology conducted to produce certain product and to test the effectiveness of the product. To produce certain product, R&D involves two kinds of analysis. The first is need analysis and the second is product analysis. Need analysis is conducted to find out the need in the field. To find

out the effectiveness of the product is done by conducting product analysis. It is done in order it can be used by the people in a certain field.

Borg and Gall (1983) developed some main stages in developing a product in Research and Development study. According to Borg and Gall, there are 10 main procedures in R&D study. Those procedures can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1. The Procedure of Research and Development by Borg and Gall (1983)

However, for some limitation and consideration, in this study, the procedures will be simplified into two main stages. Those can be seen in the following table.

Stages	Activities	Purposes	Data Resources	Technique of Data Collection	Data	Technique of Data Analysis
Exploration (Preliminary Study)	Library Research Field Research	To study the related theories and the existing materials to teach English for grade VI	Journals, textbooks, English teachers, students, and documents.	Library research, classroom observation, interview, questionnaire, document analysis.	The available materials and the implementation of teaching English in grade VI	Descriptive qualitative analysis
	Prototype development Expert judgement	To produce a prototype of the video-based textbook	The experts of material development	Interview, check list	The prototype form of the video-based textbook	Descriptive qualitative analysis
Model Development	Field try out	To get the feasibility of the video-based textbook	English teachers, students	Classroom observation, interview.	The implementation of the classroom activities provided in the video-based textbook	Descriptive qualitative analysis

Table 1. The Procedure of Study

In exploration stage the researcher conducted two kinds of research, namely library and field research. The library research was carried out to have clear information about some documents related to teaching English for young learners through journals, literature, documents, etc. Meanwhile, the researcher also obtained the data through interview and focus group discussion in order to list the students' need.

After finding out the students' need the researcher came to prototype development stage. The objective of this activity is to develop the prototype of the products needed by the students. The researcher developed the model based on the information collected from the preliminary research that is conducted in the previous stage. In order to produce good product, the researcher consulted the draft with the expert of English course book who had many experiences in composing English course

book for Primary School. It was used to find out the quality of the textbook whether it has met the criteria of good materials or not. The expert gave suggestion in terms of the strength and weaknesses of the product. The researcher revised the prototype before it was tried out to the students.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. Findings

a. Exploration

In this stage, the researcher analyzed some documents related to teaching English to young learners. The first document is the Curriculum 2013. The ministry of education excluded English from the elementary school subject. The following is the elementary school subjects based on Curriculum 2013.

Struktur Kurikulum SD/MI adalah sebagai berikut:

MATA PELAJARAN	ALOKASI WAKTU BELAJAR PER MINGGU					
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Kelompok A						
1. Pendidikan Agama dan Budi Pekerti	4	4	4	4	4	4
2. Pendidikan Pancasila dan Kewarganegaraan	5	5	6	4	4	4
3. Bahasa Indonesia	8	9	10	7	7	7
4. Matematika	5	6	6	6	6	6
5. Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam	-	-	-	3	3	3
6. Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial	-	-	-	3	3	3
Kelompok B						
1. Seni Budaya dan Prakarya	4	4	4	5	5	5
2. Pendidikan Jasmani, Olah Raga dan Kesehatan	4	4	4	4	4	4
Jumlah Alokasi Waktu Per Minggu	30	32	34	36	36	36

Keterangan:

Mata pelajaran Seni Budaya dan Prakarya dapat memuat Bahasa Daerah.

 = Pembelajaran Tematik Integratif

Figure 2. Elementary School Subjects

The above figure 1 reveals *Bahasa Indonesia* is given more time than other subjects. It is because young learners are expected to master their mother tongue better than foreign language. This policy is not applied in some private elementary schools. One of them is SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren. The result of interview towards two English teachers at SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren shows they find difficulty

in having proper materials that meet the students' need. The sixth grade students at SD Widya Wacana Jamsaren are very active and talkative. They like having fun and interesting activities such as game and role playing. They are also interested in visual teaching aids such as picture, videos, and etc. According to some students, they like learning with vocabulary rather than grammar. They need some fun and challenging activities.

The researcher analyzed some English textbooks for the sixth grade student provided in bookstore. The result was there are some English textbooks which match with the students' need namely containing contextual vocabulary, provided with picture, challenging tasks, etc. However, the materials provided in those textbooks do not cover the students of sixth grader's need yet. The students need interactive visual aids such as video in order to give clear illustration of transactional dialogues. According to the interview involving three English teachers they said They had to find another teaching resources in order to add the materials in teaching English. The textbooks do not accommodate the four skills of language, namely listening, speaking, reading, and writing. In teaching speaking skill, especially, the English teachers said that they need models in teaching speaking in terms of models of conversation in transactional and interpersonal dialogue and also spoken descriptive text which are not provided in the book. Therefore, the materials are needed to be developed in order to reach the basic competence.

Based on the above result, the researcher formulated the prototype of the product named "Rainbow 6" course book. It was video-based materials. The video contains some daily conversation based on the basic competence stated in the syllabus. The following is the example of the product.

Figure 3. Rainbow 6 Chapter 1

b. Model Development

1) Field Try Out

After getting feedback from the expert, the prototype was tried out in the classroom to get the feasibility. It was conducted with the participation of the sixth grade students of SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren. The English textbook was studied by the English teacher before it was implemented in the classroom. Before conducting the teaching and learning activity, the researcher and the English teacher were involved in an informal discussion to synchronize the perception about the materials.

The result of data findings were gathered from 1) Teacher’s interview, 2) Teacher’s questionnaire, 3) Students’ questionnaire, and 4) Observation. The details of data findings are described as follows:

a) Teacher’s Interview

The teacher was asked to give opinion about video-based textbook. The teacher said that the video-based textbook are suitable to enhance the student’s vocabulary mastery. It provides some colorful pictures and vocabulary. The teacher said that the videos are good tools to give models for the students especially for transactional dialogues.

b) Teacher's questionnaire

Based on the teacher's questionnaire the video-based textbook were good materials for elementary school students grade sixth. However, there were still some considerations that should be met. They were the duration of the video and the variation of the activity.

c) Students' questionnaire

The number of students who joint the try out were 28 students. The result questionnaire was figured in the below table.

No.	Description	YES	%	NO	%
1	The video-based textbook is interesting	26	93	2	7
2	The video-based textbook improves the students' motivation to learn English	23	83	5	17
3	The video-based textbook can improves the students' vocabulary	22	80	6	20
4	The duration of the video is sufficient	25	90	3	10

Table 2. The result of the students' questionnaire

The above table shows that 26 students argued that the video-based textbook is interesting for them. 23 students said that the materials can motivate them. There are 22 students said that their vocabulary improved significantly. The duration of the video was sufficient as said by 25 students while 3 students said that the duration was a bit too long.

d) Observation

The try out was held in the 6-A grade in SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren Surakarta. Based on the observation, the researcher found that the students enjoyed the teaching and learning process using the video-based textbook. They really paid attention while the video was displayed by the teacher.

c. Evaluation and Revision

During the field try out, the researcher took her role as the observer to see whether the textbook worked well in the classroom or not. The researcher observed the English teacher and the students. To know the feedback from the English teacher, after each field try out, the evaluation section was carried out involving the students, English teacher, expert, and the researcher. The information collected from the evaluation was used to revise the prototype.

Through the product evaluation, the researcher was able to formulate the strength and weaknesses of the prototype. In the revision section, the researcher did some changes to the prototype based on the need of the English teacher.

2. Discussion

As it has been mentioned earlier that the purpose of the study was to develop video-based textbook to teach English for elementary school. This development was based on library research and need analysis beforehand. Based on the need analysis, some English teachers coming at SD Kristen Widya Wacana Jamsaren said that they needed models to teach English for their students in which give the students example on how to pronounce the vocabulary and structure of sentences. It is in line with Williams and Lutes (2009) who states that there are some benefits in using video as a teaching tool.

- a. Video materials can focus on information that cannot be readily presented in a traditional classroom because of constraints such as size, location, costs, etc.
- b. Video materials present the same target structures and vocabulary in anew medium that allows for core repetition of the target language before learner attention is diverted or lost.

- c. Video materials are excellent method of exposing language learners to language used in a wide variety of contexts because of the variety of selections available.
- d. The students have the opportunity to observe more authentic materials

However, “Rainbow 6” video-based textbook still had some weaknesses. This material could not be used in every school because it depended on the equipment such as computer, laptop, LCD projector, and loud speaker. The teacher should also modify the speaking activity in order to make the atmosphere of the class alive so the goals of the teaching and learning can be achieved.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, the video-based textbook tries to provide both the teacher and students the materials to improve the students’ vocabulary. It was developed from the library research and need analysis.

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